

**CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BALANCE OF SYMPATHETIC
AND PARASYMPATHETIC NERVOUS SYSTEM IN PATIENTS
WITH CHRONIC HEPATOPATHIES**

***Caracteristici ale echilibrului sistemului nervos simpatic și parasimpatic
la pacienții cu hepatopatii cronice***

CZU: 616.36-036.12:616.839

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20156434

Elena BEREZOVSICAIA

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0360-745X>

scientific researcher, Laboratory of Gastroenterology, "Nicolae Testemițanu" SUMP

E-mail: elena.berezovscaia@usmf.md

Iulianna LUPASCO

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1282-5080>

dr. hab. med. sci., Principal scientific researcher, Laboratory of Gastroenterology,

"Nicolae Testemițanu" SUMP

E-mail: labgastroenterologie@usmf.md

Liudmila GOLOVATIUC

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5570-625X>

scientific researcher, Laboratory of Gastroenterology, "Nicolae Testemițanu" SUMP

E-mail: liudmila.golovatiuc@usmf.md

Inna VENGHER

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9702-1059>

dr. med. sci., Coordinator scientific researcher, Laboratory of Gastroenterology,

"Nicolae Testemițanu" SUMP

E-mail: inna.vengher@gmail.com

Summary. Chronic hepatopathies present one of the important medical issues in Moldova, occupying a leading place in terms of incidence and severity. The aim was to study the balance of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system in patients with chronic hepatopathies of various etiologies. A total of 59 patients were examined: I-st group: 34 patients with chronic HBV infection, II-nd group: 25 with Metabolic Dysfunction-Associated Steatotic Liver Disease (MASLD), 26 practically healthy individuals formed the control group (CG). All participants were assessed for diastolic blood pressure (DBP), pulse rate (PR) and Kerdo Vegetative Index (KVI).

The highest average DBP values were observed in Group I, the lowest - in CG. The highest average PR values were determined in Group II, in Group I and CG were significantly lower. Average KVI values revealed the prevalence of vagotonia in individuals with chronic HBV infection, normotonia with a tendency to sympathicotonia in patients with MASLD and normotonia in CG. In patients with chronic HBV viral infection, the vagosympathetic balance was shifted towards vagotonia, and in patients with MASLD, a tendency to sympathicotonia was noted. The KVI indicator can be used as an additional non-invasive method for diagnosing chronic hepatopathies.

Key words: chronic hepatopathies, blood pressure, pulse rate, Kerdo Vegetative Index.

Introduction

Chronic hepatopathy is a significant problem of modern medicine. The prevalence of liver pathology is steadily increasing from year to year and has now acquired the appearance of a pandemic. For 25 years, liver pathology has been one of the leading places in the Republic of Moldova in terms of prevalence, severity, frequency of chronicity and disability. For about 30 years, chronic diffuse liver diseases have been ranked 3rd in the structure of mortality among the adult population of the Republic of Moldova. Thus, chronic hepatopathies present one of the most severe and important medical and social problems of our time.

At the same time, despite the large number of scientific studies on liver pathology, the overwhelming majority of them are aimed at studying clinical features, changing laboratory and instrumental peculiarities and studying new methods of treatment. Meanwhile, physiological parameters in patients with chronic hepatopathies are extremely rarely considered in modern literature. The role of the autonomic nervous system in liver functioning is not clear enough. Although it is known that both the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems are present in the liver, the CNS receives information from the liver about osmolality, glucose and lipid concentrations through afferent neurons, and liver itself, in turn, receives various signals through efferent neurons that affect blood flow, bile secretion and metabolism¹. Studies on the balance of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems in liver pathology most often concern toxic liver damage². Thus, determining the vagosympathetic balance is an important point in chronic hepatopathies.

The aim of the work: to study the balance of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system in patients with chronic hepatopathies of various etiologies.

Materials and Methods

To clarify the features of the vagosympathetic balance, 59 adult patients with various chronic hepatopathies were examined; two groups were formed according to the etiological factor: Group I included 34 patients with chronic infection caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV); Group II – 25 patients with Metabolic Dysfunction-Associated Steatotic Liver Disease (MASLD); 26 practically healthy individuals formed the control group (CG).

The diagnosis of liver pathology was established during an outpatient appointment, taking into account clinical and paraclinical data. Criteria for inclusion in the study and exclusion from it were determined. An informed voluntary consent for participation in the study was drawn up and signed with each participant.

Physiological characteristics were evaluated in all participants, including diastolic blood pressure (DBP), pulse rate (PR), and then the Kerdo Vegetative Index (KVI) was calculated.

Statistical analysis included descriptive and comparative methods of analyzing the obtained results. The data are presented in the format $M \pm m$, where M is the arithmetic mean,

¹ Mizuno, K., & Ueno, Y. Autonomic Nervous System and the Liver: in: *Hepatology research: the official journal of the Japan Society of Hepatology*, 2017, vol. 47, no.2, pp. 160-165. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hepr.12760>. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/hepr.12760>

² Akalaev R.N., Sharipova V.Kh., Stopnitskiy A.A., Khozhiev Kh.Sh. Assessment of effect of chronic alcohol intoxication on certain parameters of the autonomic nervous system and cognitive functions, in: *Messenger of anesthesiology and resuscitation*, 2020, vol 17, no.3, pp. 32-38. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.21292/2078-5658-2020-17-3-32-38>. URL: <https://www.vair-journal.com/jour/article/view/436>

m is the standard error of the mean. The formula for calculating the Kerdo vegetative index: $KVI = (1 - DBP/PR) \times 100\%$; where: DBP is diastolic pressure (mm Hg), PR is pulse rate (beats per minute)³. The nonparametric Mann-Whitney U-test was used to determine the level of statistical significance of differences in the studied characteristics (p), taking into account the small sample size, as well as the fact that the distribution of the characteristic in the studied groups differed from normal⁴. Statistical analysis of the results was performed using built-in functions and the Data Analysis Excel 365 statistical data processing package.

The survey methods were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of SUMF "Nicolae Testemițanu" No. 103 from 30.11.2024.

The article was implemented within the framework of the institutional project "Interaction between metabolic, nutritional and psychological sciences in the field of steatotic disorders, development of biological principles in disease management" at the Laboratory of Gastroenterology within the Center for Abdominal Pathology and Transplantation (080401)

Results and discussion

The average DBP values in patients from group I (Figure 1) were $82,66 \pm 1,66$ mm Hg, and in group II – $77,28 \pm 2,38$ mm Hg, the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0,05$). The lowest DBP values were found in practically healthy individuals of the control group ($74,23 \pm 1,05$ mm Hg), and the differences of CG with both groups of patients with hepatopathies were statistically significant ($p(I) < 0,001$; $p(II) < 0,05$).

Blood pressure is the main indicator reflecting the adaptation of the circulatory system to the body needs. Diastolic pressure reflects the degree of vascular resistance and the general condition of the vascular system. The authors note that high blood pressure is often observed and is included in the diagnostic criteria of metabolic syndrome, which often accompanies fatty liver disease⁵.

The pulse rate (Figure 2) was higher in group II ($81,7 \pm 1,7$ beats /min), which is significantly higher than in group I and in CG ($p(I) < 0,001$; $p(CG) < 0,001$), in which this indicator was $74,2 \pm 1,3$ beats /min and $74,3 \pm 0,9$ beats /min ($p > 0,05$), respectively.

Pulse palpation is known as one of the oldest and most valuable methods of examination used in medicine, and today, in the era of modern research, it remains a simple and convenient way to obtain valuable information about both the activity of the heart and the state of blood circulation. The pulse rate depends on many factors, including the state of the autonomic nervous system. Pulse is an indicator that characterizes the

³ Akalaev R.N., Sharipova V.Kh., Stopnitskiy A.A., Khozhiev Kh.Sh. Assessment of effect of chronic alcohol intoxication on certain parameters of the autonomic nervous system and cognitive functions, in: *Messenger of anesthesiology and resuscitation*, 2020, vol 17, no. 3, pp. 32-38. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.21292/2078-5658-2020-17-3-32-38>. URL: <https://www.vair-journal.com/jour/article/view/436>

⁴ Garrocho-Rangel A, Aranda-Romo S, Martínez-Martínez R, Zavala-Alonso V, Flores-Arriaga JC & Pozos-Guillén A. Fundamentals of Nonparametric Statistical Tests for Dental Clinical Research, in: *Dentistry journal*, 2024, vol. 12, no. 10, art/no. 314. <https://doi.org/10.3390/dj12100314>. URL: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11506617/>

⁵ Ciardullo S., Grassi G., Mancina G., and Perseghin G. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease and risk of incident hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis, in: *Eur. J. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, Apr. 2022, vol. 34, no. 4, p. 365, DOI: 10.1097/MEG.0000000000002299. URL: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34678858/>

volume of blood flow in the state of maximum ejection (systole). According to J.M. Mangrum et al. (2000), the “normal” pulse range is from 50 to 95 beats per minute⁶.

Analyzing the results obtained by calculating the Kerdo Vegetative Index (Figure 3), it should be noted that vagotonia prevailed in patients with chronic HBV infection, their average values were $(-11,93) \pm 1,87\%$, and the possibility of error in comparison with individuals with MASLD and the control group was significantly small (p (II) $< 0,01$; p (CG) $< 0,01$). Normotonia was observed in patients with MASLD and practically healthy individuals, the average values for this indicator were $4,93 \pm 2,52\%$ and $0,05 \pm 1,04\%$, respectively, at the same time it should be noted that in the group of patients with MASLD there was a tendency towards sympathicotonia, the reliability of differences between group II and CG was higher than 95%.

KVI is an integral indicator that allows assessing the functional state of various processes in human organism, indirectly characterizing the vagosympathetic balance of the body and can be recommended for assessing the balance of the tone of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. The vegetative index is within the range from -10% to +10% (normal). A positive value of the index indicates a shift in the balance towards sympathicotonia, a negative value indicates the predominance of vagotonia⁷.

Figure 1. Diastolic (DBP) blood pressure values in the study groups

Figure 2. Pulse rate values in the study groups

There is an opinion that the prevalence of sympathicotonia in patients with MASLD can be considered an unfavorable prognostic criterion, since the increased influence of the sympathetic nervous system leads to hypotonic and hypokinetic disorders. In addition,

⁶ Mangrum J. M. and DiMarco J. P. The evaluation and management of bradycardia, in: *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 2000, vol. 342, no. 10, pp. 703–709, doi: 10.1056/NEJM200003093421006.

⁷ Вагин Ю.Е., Деунезева С.М., Хлытина А.А. Вегетативный индекс Кердо: роль исходных параметров, области и ограничения применения, in: *Физиология человека*, 2021, Том 47, №. 1, pp. 31–42, doi: 10.31857/S0131164620060120.

tion, there is an opinion that stimulation of the vagus nerve protects the liver from damage by enhancing anti-inflammatory, anti-apoptotic properties, increasing antioxidant activity⁸.

Figure 3. Kerdo's Vegetative Index (KVI) in the study groups

Conclusion.

It was found the disbalance of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system in patients with chronic hepatopathies. In patients with chronic HBV viral infection, the vagosympathetic balance was shifted towards vagotonia, while in patients with MASLD, a tendency towards sympathicotonia was noted. The Kerdo vegetative index can be used as an additional non-invasive method for diagnosing chronic hepatopathies.

⁸ Metz CN, Pavlov VA. Vagus nerve cholinergic circuitry to the liver and the gastrointestinal tract in the neuroimmune communicatome, in: *Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol.*, 2018, vol. 315, no. 5, pp: G651-G658. doi: 10.1152/ajpgi.00195.2018. URL: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6293249/>.